

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Internet Of Things (IOT)

The **Internet of things** is the network of physical devices, vehicles, and other items embedded with electronics, software, sensors, actuators and network connectivity which enable these objects to collect and exchange data.

IoT (Internet of Things) is an advanced automation and analytics system which exploits networking, sensing, big data, and artificial intelligence technology to deliver complete systems for a product or service. These systems allow greater transparency, control, and performance when applied to any industry or system. IoT systems have applications across industries through their unique flexibility and ability to be suitable in any environment. They enhance data collection, automation, operations, and much more through smart devices and powerful enabling technology. This tutorial aims to provide you with a thorough introduction to IoT. It introduces the **key concepts** of IoT, necessary in using and deploying IoT systems. The most important features of IoT include artificial intelligence, connectivity, sensors, active engagement, and small device use. A brief review of these features is given below:

AI – IoT essentially makes virtually anything “smart”, meaning it enhances every aspect of life with the power of data collection, artificial intelligence algorithms, and networks. This can mean something as simple as enhancing your refrigerator and cabinets to detect when milk and your favorite cereal run low, and to then place an order with your preferred grocer.

Connectivity – New enabling technologies for networking, and specifically IoT networking, mean networks are no longer exclusively tied to major providers. Networks can exist on a much smaller and cheaper scale while still being practical. IoT creates these small networks between its system devices.

Sensors – IoT loses its distinction without sensors.

1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

Yellow leaf disease of sugarcane is an important and widely spreaded disease causing severe yield losses. Sugarcane yellow leaf virus (ScYLV) is present in many sugarcane growing areas of the world. It is suspected to cause yellow leaf disease (formerly called YLS, yellow leaf syndrome) of sugarcane. This study investigated symptom expression in a selection of cultivars classified into three groups; ScYLV-susceptible/infected, ScYLV-resistant and intermediately infected cultivars grown in plantation fields in the islands of Hawaii. Incidence of yellow leaf symptoms was correlated, though not tightly, to the presence of ScYLV. The correlation is based on two factors:

- (i) ScYLV-infected cultivars (from both susceptible and intermediate groups) showed severe symptom expression.
- (ii) ScYLV-infected plants had four times higher symptom incidence than virus-free plants of the same cultivar.

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Plant disease identification by visual way is more laborious task and at the same time, less accurate and can be done only in limited areas. Whereas if automatic detection technique is used it will take less efforts, less time and become more accurate. In plants, some general diseases seen are brown and yellow spots, early and late scorch, and others are fungal, viral and bacterial diseases. Image processing is used for measuring affected area of disease and to determine the difference in the color of the affected area Image segmentation is the process of separating or grouping an image into different parts.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1: A Modern Approach for Plant Leaf Disease Classification which depends on leaf image processing

Author: Chaitali G. Dhaware, K.H. Wanjale

Year of publication:2017

Agrarian production is that trait on which our nation's economy immensely depends. This is the motivation that recognition of leaves unhealthiness is the solution for saving the reduction of crops and productivity. It requisite enormous amount of work, mastery in the leaf diseases, and additionally need the extreme amount of time. Thus, image processing techniques are applied for the discovering and recognition of plant leaf unhealthiness. Recognition of plant leaf diseases along some automatic method is useful as it decrease a huge effort of observing in large farms, and at initial phase itself it identify the signs of diseases. Plant leaf disease detection and identification includes the stages like image acquisition, image pre-processing, image segmentation, feature extraction and classification. This paper discusses techniques for image pre-processing, image segmentation algorithm used for automatic recognition and research on various plant leaf disease classification algorithms that may be used for leaves disease classification.

In proposed work the primary stage is the acquisition of leaf images with the use of mobile camera which have minimum 2 megapixels and above resolution. The dataset consists of healthy leaves and infected leaves images. In next stage the pre-processing techniques are apply on input leaves images for better results in next processing. Image resizing is one of the major tasks in order to keep up the consistency as far as size of the images.

Paper 2: Disease Detection on the Leaves of the Tomato Plants by Using Deep Learning

Author: Halil Durmuú, Ece Olcay Güneú, Mürvet KÖrcÖ

Year of publication:2017

The aim of this work is to detect diseases that occur on plants in tomato fields or in their greenhouses. For this purpose, deep learning was used to detect the various diseases on the leaves of tomato plants. In the study, it was aimed that the deep learning algorithm should be run in real time on the robot. So the robot will be able to detect the diseases of the plants while wandering manually or autonomously on the field or in the greenhouse. Likewise, diseases can also be detected from close-up photographs taken from plants by sensors built in fabricated greenhouses. The examined diseases in this study cause physical changes in the leaves of the tomato plant. These changes on the leaves can be seen with RGB cameras. In the previous studies, standard feature extraction methods on plant leaf images to detect diseases have been used. In this study, deep learning methods were used to detect diseases.

Deep learning architecture selection was the key issue for the implementation. So that, two different deep learning network architectures were tested first AlexNet and then SqueezeNet. For both of these deep learning networks training and validation were done on the Nvidia Jetson TX1. Tomato leaf images from the PlantVillage dataset has been used for the training. Ten different classes including healthy images are used. Trained networks are also tested on the images from the internet.

Paper 3: Recent Machine Learning Based Approaches For Disease Detection and Classification of Agricultural products

Author : Mukesh Kumar Tripathi, Dhananjay D. Maktedar

Year of publication : 2016

Disease infection to agricultural products like plants, fruits and vegetables, results in degradation of quality and quantity of agriculture products. This directly affects the financial source of agriculturists and the human health. Hence, detection of diseases in plants, fruits and vegetables crops at early stages of development leads to reduce loss of yield and quality. The traditional approaches for disease detection requires continues monitoring and observation of farms either by farmers or by experts. But, it is very costly and time consuming. In last few years, various researchers have focused into this area to provide optimized solution.

Popular methods have utilized machine learning, image processing and classification based approaches to identify and detect the diseases on agricultural products. The existing techniques for disease detection have utilized various image processing methods followed by various classification techniques. This paper presents an overview of existing reported techniques useful in detection of diseases of agricultural products. A comparative study of different methods based on the type of agricultural product, methodology and its efficiency together with the advantages and disadvantages is also included in this paper.

Paper 4 : Detection of Plant Leaf Diseases Using Image Segmentation and Soft Computing Techniques:

Author : Vijai Singh, A.K. Misra

Year of publication : 2016

The agricultural land mass is more than just being a feeding sourcing in today's world. Indian economy is highly dependent of agricultural productivity. Therefore in field of agriculture, detection of disease in plants plays an important role. To detect a plant disease in very initial stage, use of automatic disease detection technique is beneficial. For instance a disease named little leaf disease is a hazardous disease found in pine trees in United States. The affected tree has a stunted growth and dies within 6 years. Its impact is found in Alabama, Georgia parts of Southern US. In such scenarios early detection could have been fruitful. The existing method for plant disease detection is simply naked eye observation by experts through which identification and detection of plant diseases is done. For doing so, a large team of experts as well as continuous monitoring of plant is required, which costs very high when we do with large farms.

At the same time, in some countries, farmers do not have proper facilities or even idea that they can contact to experts. Due to which consulting experts even cost high as well as time consuming too. In such conditions, the suggested technique proves to be beneficial in monitoring large fields of crops. Automatic detection of the diseases by just seeing the symptoms on the plant leaves makes it easier as well as cheaper. This also supports machine vision to provide image based automatic process control, inspection, and robot guidance

Paper 5: Detection and Classification of Disease Affected Region of Plant Leaves using Image Processing Technique:

Author : AI-Hiary

Year of publication : 2016

The proposed image processing technique is presented for plant leaf disease detection and classification. Here, image acquisition is performed by considering RGB colour based disease affected leaf image. Histogram Equalization is used to further enhance the image contrast. K-means clustering is used to divide the image into parts. Image feature extraction is performed to extract the features of leaf disease symptoms. Support Vector Machine is used for the leaf disease detection & classification and finally ant colony optimization is applied for the optimization of concept. In this proposed approach, major disease detection, classification & optimization is performed by SVM and ACO.

Support Vector Machine is statistical learning concept used as the classification and regression models. Ant Colony Optimization is swarm intelligence based concept well known for the local and global best optimized search solution. Here, we have considered ACO approach to optimize the solution upto the maximum possible iterations for plant leaf disease detection. In this proposed concept, disease affected leaf image is considered as the input and possible disease type is determined as output with the percentage of disease affected portion. Image segmentation is performed by making use of k-means clustering. Image feature extraction is performed to obtain the features of leaf disease symptoms. Image classification is performed using support vector machine and finally ant colony optimization is performed for the optimization of concept.

**Paper 6 : Sugarcane Leaf Disease Detection and Severity Estimation Based
On Segmented Spots Image:**

Author : Evy Kamilah Ratnasari

Year of publication : 2014

Plant disease severity estimation is an important step in sugarcane breeding process to get the best variety that robust to disease. The disease in sugarcane plant is not only reducing the yield but also deteriorating of the variety. The sugarcane production quality is depend on its robustness of the disease. With about 15% of sugarcane spots disease infection on leaves, sugarcane production has significant severe loss . To control these disease and minimize the infection of whole sugarcane plantation, the disease must be identified and treated earlier.

There are three major spot disease types, namely rust spot, yellow spot, and ring spot, which infect the tropical yield. The symptom of these fungi-caused diseases appears on a leaf as unique spots. These spots can be manually recognized based on the spot characteristics. However, this manual recognition has its limitation that may harm the efforts in many cases. There are three major spot disease types, namely rust spot, yellow spot, and ring spot, which infect the tropical yield. The symptom of these fungi-caused diseases appears on a leaf as unique spots. These spots can be manually recognized based on the spot characteristics. However, this manual recognition has its limitation that may harm the efforts in many cases. Manual detection and estimation by the naked eye observations are subjective and it is not possible to identify the disease accurately. Since utilizing pesticide for plant disease treatment increases the danger of toxic residue level on agricultural product, contaminates the ground water, and it needs more production cost if it is not treated accordingly, the precision analysis using computer.

Paper 7 : Fast and Accurate Detection and Classification of Plant Diseases

Author : AI-Hiary

Year of publication : 2011

We propose and experimentally evaluate a software solution for automatic detection and classification of plant leaf diseases. The proposed solution is an improvement to the solution proposed in [1] as it provides faster and more accurate solution. The developed processing scheme consists of four main phases as in [1]. The following two steps are added successively after the segmentation phase. In the first step we identify the mostly green colored pixels. Next, these pixels are masked based on specific threshold values that are computed using Otsu's method, then those mostly green pixels are masked. The other additional step is that the pixels with zeros red, green and blue values and the pixels on the boundaries of the infected cluster (object) were completely removed. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed technique is a robust technique for the detection of plant leaves diseases. The developed algorithm's efficiency can successfully detect and classify the examined diseases with a precision between 83% and 94%, and can achieve 20% speedup over the approach proposed.

Plant diseases have turned into a dilemma as it can cause significant reduction in both quality and quantity of agricultural products [20]. It is estimated that 2007 plant disease losses in Georgia (USA) is approximately \$539.74 million. Of this amount, around 185 million USD was spent on controlling the diseases, and the rest is the value of damage caused by the diseases.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

The set of disease that are effected to the sugarcane plant .in existing system yellow leaf virus is detected in sugarcane plant as it is the common disease that effects sugarcane.The disease effected to the plant when the resistance is decreased and disease may spread continuously and the rate of damage will increase.Here they are using algorithm for detecting only one virus. Yellow leaf of sugarcane is an emerging viral disease whose causal agent is a Polerovirus, the Sugar-cane yellow leaf virus (SCYLV) transmitted by aphids. To identify quantitative trait loci controlling resistance to yellow leaf which are of direct relevance for breeding, we undertook a genome-wide association study (GWAS) on sugarcane cultivar panel.

3.1.1 Limitations of existing system:

- 1.It can identify only yellow leaf virus in sugarcane disease .
- 2.It is not efficient when the number of disease increases .

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

In our system the detection disease is done by using Discrete wavelenght transform(DWT) algorithm. There are some set of diseases in the database and check with the already stored inputs images. Digital camera or similar devices are use to take images of leafs of different types, and then those are used to identify the affected area in leafs. Then different types of image-processing techniques are applied on them, to process those images, to get different and useful features needed for the purpose of analyzing later. Algorithm written below illustrated the step by step approach for the proposed image recognition and segmentation processes:

1) Image acquisition is the very first step that requires capturing an image with the help of a digital camera.

2) Preprocessing of input image to improve the quality of image and to remove the undesired distortion from the image. Clipping of the leaf image is performed to get the interested image region and then image smoothing is done using the smoothing filter. To increase the contrast Image enhancement is also done.

3) Mostly green colored pixels, in this step, are masked. In this, we computed a threshold value that is used for these pixels. Then in the following way mostly green pixels are masked: if pixel intensity of the green component is less than the pre-computed threshold value, then zero value is assigned to the red, green and blue components of the this pixel.

4) In the infected clusters, inside the boundaries, remove the masked cells.

5) Obtain the useful segments to classify the leaf diseases. Segment the components using DWT algorithm.

System takes lots of infected part images from crops,are else downloaded from the flickr and google and those images are going through the image

processing techniques .In the recent times improving the accuracy is main thing to detect the disease faster. Image segmentation is main technique to detect the affected area using threshold value.Here according to the pixel of the image the threshold value have to be assigned to every image.According to that the system will compare all images that saved in the dataset.By using DWT algorithm the pixel of the image is to be compared and remove the unused pixels using fourier transform by forming a matrix over the image.Most of the plants will be in green pixels. If the color changed means that part is affected by some virus or fungus.The proposed method is the improvement of the approach which will increase the accuracy and quality of the image.According to the severity of the situation the system will give the simple recommendations and notifications to suggest some pesticides and mention the fungus that is affected.

The proposed integrated concept is used to detect plant leaf diseases. For this, we have considered the expert dataset having leaf of thirteen different types of diseases (Eyespot Disease,Leaf Scald, Mosaic, Orange Rust ,Pokkah Boeng Disease, Ratoon Stunting ,Red Rot Disease, Ring Spot,Smut Disease, Yellow Leaf Disease ,brown stipe). In this concept, we have considered the dataset images of mainly fungal and bacterial, Viral affected leaf images. Yellow virus is bacteria affected leaf disease. Gummerealla sacharri, Fungal Leaf Spot and Fungus Anthracnose are fungus affected leaf diseases. In this dataset, some healthy leaf images are also considered for the evaluation of results.

3.2.1 Advantages of proposed system

1. It will detect the more diseases in the sugarcane plant
- 2.The system detect the disease that effected to the plant
- 3.It will improve the production quality

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The objective of feasibility study is not only to solve the problem but also to acquire a sense of its scope. During the study, the problem definition was crystalized and aspects of the problem to be included in the system are determined. Consequently benefits are estimated with greater accuracy at this stage. The key considerations are:

- Economic feasibility
- Technical feasibility
- Operational feasibility

Economic Feasibility

Economic feasibility studies not only the cost of hardware, software is included but also the benefits in the form that this project, if installed will reduce the time consuming and increasing the speed of work.

Technical Feasibility

Technical feasibility evaluates the hardware requirements, software technology, available personnel etc, as per the requirements it provides sufficient memory to hold and process the data as it uses SQL Server, as the back end. Technically it is feasible as it platform independent, It can be used by all the users for keyword searching after their request accepted by the data owners.

Operational Feasibility

Proposed system is beneficial only if they can be turned into information systems, which will meet the organization requirements. This system supports in producing relevant search results of the users. It consumes less time to find relevant results for user. Thus the proposed project can be put in place without any difficulties.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 4.1: System Architecture

4.2 UML DAIGRAMS

4.2.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM

Fig 4.2 Use Case Diagram

4.2.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

Fig 4.3 Sequence Diagram

4.2.3 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

Fig 4.4 Activity Diagram

4.2.4 CLASS DIAGRAM

Fig 4.5 Class Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 Hardware Requirements

The most common set of requirements is defined by the any system or the software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware, a hardware requirements list is often accompanied by a hardware compatability list (HCL), especially in case of operating systems. An HCL lists tested, compatible, and sometimes incompatible hardware devices for a particular operating system or application.

- Processor : Core 2 Duo
- Motherboard : Genuine Intel
- RAM : Min 1 GB
- Hard Disk : 120 GB

5.2 Software Requirements

The software requirements deals with defining software resource requirements and prerequisites that needs to be installed on a computer to provide optimal functioning of an application. These requirements or prerequisites are generally not included in the software installation package and needed to be installed seperately before the software is installed.

- Operating system : Windows 7
- Technology Used : JSP & Servlet
- IDE : MATLAB
- Database : MySQL Query Browser
- Browser : Chrome or Firefox

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 MATLAB

MATLAB handles simple numerical expressions and mathematical formulas. The name MATLAB stands for MATRIX LABORATORY. matlab was written originally to provide easy access to matrix software developed by the LINPACK (linear system package) and EISPACK (Eigen system package) projects.

Matlab is a high-performance language for technical computing. It integrates computation, visualization, and programming environment. Furthermore, matlab is a modern programming language environment: it has sophisticated data structures, contains built-in editing and debugging tools, and supports object-oriented programming. These factors make matlab an excellent tool for teaching and research. matlab has many advantages compared to conventional computer languages (e.g., C, FORTRAN) for solving technical problems. matlab is an interactive system whose basic data element is an array that does not require dimensioning. The software package has been commercially available since 1984 and is now considered as a standard tool at most universities and industries worldwide.

It has powerful built-in routines that enable a very wide variety of computations. It also has easy to use graphics commands that make the visualization of results immediately available. Specific applications are collected in packages referred to as toolbox.

There are toolboxes for signal processing, symbolic computation, control theory, simulation, optimization, and several other fields of applied science and engineering.

The MATLAB Platform

MATLAB has an excellent set of graphic tools. Plotting a given data set or the results of computation is possible with very few commands. You are highly encouraged to plot mathematical functions and results of analysis as often as possible. Trying to understand mathematical equations with graphics is an enjoyable and very efficient way of learning mathematic.

Matrices are the basic elements of the MATLAB environment. A matrix is a two-dimensional array consisting of m rows and n columns. Special cases are column vectors ($n = 1$) and row vectors ($m = 1$).

MATLAB is a tool for technical computing, computation and visualization in an integrated environment, e.g.,

- Math and computation
- Algorithm development
- Data acquisition
- Modeling , simulation, and prototyping
- Data analysis, exploration, and visualization
- Scientific and engineering graphics
- Application development, including graphical user interface building

6.1.2 MySQL Database

MySQL is a fast, easy-to-use RDBMS being used for many small and big businesses. MySQL is developed, marketed, and supported by MySQL AB, which is a Swedish company.

6.2 MODULES DESCRIPTION

- 1. Image acquisition**
- 2. Image pre-processing**
- 3. Image segmentation**
- 4. Classification**
- 5. Feature extraction**
- 6. Disease detection**

1. Image acquisition

Before any video or image processing can commence an image must be captured by a camera and converted into a manageable entity. This is the process known as image acquisition.

The image acquisition process consists of three steps; energy reflected from the object of interest, an optical system which focuses the energy and finally a sensor which measures the amount of energy. The three steps are shown for the case of an ordinary camera with the sun as the energy source. To capture an image we need some kind of energy source to illuminate the scene. After having illuminated the object of interest, the light reflected from the object now has to be captured by the camera.

The light reflected from the object of interest is focused by some optics and now needs to be recorded by the camera. To transform the information from the sensor into an image, each cell content is now converted into a pixel value in the range.

First we need to select the plant which is affected by the disease and then collect the leaf of the plant and take a snapshot of leaf and load the leaf image into the system.

Image acquisition			
Lighting	Camera configuration	Synchronization	Storage

Fig 6.1 Image Acquisition

2. Image pre-processing

Image pre-processing may have dramatic positive effects on the quality of feature extraction and the results of image analysis. Image pre-processing is analogous to the mathematical normalization of a data set, which is a common step in many feature descriptor methods. Volume control with a simple tone knob; volume control plus treble, bass, and mid; or volume control plus a full graphics equalizer, effects processing, and great speakers in an acoustically superior room. In that way, this chapter promotes image pre-processing by describing a combination of corrections and enhancements that are an essential part of a computer vision pipeline.

Enhancements are used to optimize for specific feature measurement methods, rather than fix problems. Familiar image processing enhancements include sharpening and color balancing. In image processing, filters are mainly used to suppress either the high frequencies in the image, i.e. smoothing the image, or the low frequencies, i.e. enhancing or detecting edges in the image. Image restoration and enhancement techniques are described in both the spatial domain and frequency domain, i.e. Fourier transforms. However, Fourier transforms require substantial computations, and in some cases are not worth the effort. Multiplication in the frequency domain corresponds to convolution in the time and the spatial domain.

Fig 6.2 Image Pre-Processing

3. Image segmentation

Image segmentation is the process of partition of image into different segments. It use to get some meaningful information from segmented image. Here we are using DWT algorithm. The Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), based on time-scale representation, provides efficient multi-resolution subband decomposition of signals. It has become a powerful tool for signal processing and finds numerous applications in various fields such as audio compression, pattern recognition, texture discrimination, computer graphics etc. Specifically the 2-D DWT and its counterpart 2- D Inverse DWT (IDWT) play a significant role in many image/video coding applications. The DWT architecture, the input image is decomposed into high pass and low pass components using HPF and LPF filters giving rise to the first level of hierarchy. The process is continued until multiple hierarchies are obtained. A1 and D1 are the approximation and detail filters.

In Fourier analysis, the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) decompose a signal into sinusoidal basis functions of different frequencies. No information is lost in this transformation; in other words, we can completely recover the original signal from its DFT (FFT) representation. In wavelet analysis, the

Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) decomposes a signal into a set of mutually orthogonal wavelet basis functions. These functions differ from sinusoidal basis functions in that they are spatially localized – that is, nonzero over only part of the total signal length. Furthermore, wavelet functions are dilated, translated and scaled versions of a common function ϕ , known as the mother wavelet. As is the case in Fourier analysis, the DWT is invertible, so that the original signal can be completely recovered from its DWT representation.

Fig 6.3 Image Segmentation

4. Classification

Classification is assigning pixels in the image to categories or classes of interest. In order to classify a set of data into different classes or categories, the relationship between the data and the classes into which they are classified must be well understood. This set of notes presents the Support Vector Machine (SVM) learning algorithm. SVMs are among the best and many believe are indeed the best “off-the-shelf” supervised learning algorithm. To tell the SVM story, we’ll need to first talk about margins and the idea of separating data with a large “gap.” The optimal margin classifier, which will lead into a digression on Lagrange duality. Kernels, which give a way to apply SVMs efficiently in very high dimensional (such as infinite dimensional) feature spaces, and finally, we’ll close off the story with the SMO algorithm, which gives an efficient implementation of SVMs.

Fig 6.4 Image Classification

5. Feature extraction

In feature extraction we are doing the color co-occurrence method for extracting the both color and texture are taken in to account to get a unique feature that image for that RGB is converted into HSI translation. According to the pixel range the specific values are to be arranged and then compared with the image which is already saved in the data set.

Feature extraction is done after the preprocessing phase in character recognition system. The primary task of pattern recognition is to take an input pattern and correctly assign it as one of the possible output classes. This process can be divided into two general stages: Feature selection and Classification.

Feature selection is critical to the whole process since the classifier will not be able to recognize from poorly selected features. Criteria to choose features given by Lippman are: Features should contain information required to distinguish between classes, be insensitive to irrelevant variability in the input, and also be limited in number, to permit, efficient computation of discriminant functions and to limit the amount of training data required”

Feature extraction is an important step in the construction of any pattern classification and aims at the extraction of the relevant information that characterizes each class. In this process relevant features are extracted from objects/ alphabets to form feature vectors. These feature vectors are then used

by classifiers to recognize the input unit with target output unit. It becomes easier for the classifier to classify between different classes by looking at these features as it allows fairly easy to distinguish. A good feature set contains discriminating information, which can distinguish one object from other objects. It must be as robust as possible in order to prevent generating different feature codes for the objects in the same class.

Fig 6.5 Feature Extraction

6. Disease detection

Image process is the use of computer algorithms to perform image process on digital pictures. It permits a far wider vary of algorithms to be applied to the computer file and might avoid issues like the build-up of noise and signal distortion throughout process. Digital image process has terribly important role in agriculture field. It's widely accustomed observe the crop disease with high accuracy. Detection and recognition of diseases in plants mistreatment digital image method is extremely effective in providing symptoms of characteristic diseases at its early stages. Plant pathologists will analyze the digital pictures mistreatment digital image process for diagnosing of crop diseases.

Fig 6.6 Disease Detection

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 TESTING OBJECTIVES

Testing is a set of activities that can be planned in advance and conducted systematically. For this reason a template for software testing, a set of steps into which we can place specific test case design techniques and testing methods should be defined for software process. The software, which has been developed, has to be tested to prove its validity. Testing is considered to be the least creative phase of the whole cycle of system design. Testing often accounts for more effort than any other software engineering activity. If it is conducted haphazardly, time is wasted, unnecessary effort is expended, and even worse, errors sneak through undetected. It would therefore seem reasonable to establish a systematic strategy for testing software.

Type of Testing

There are two type of testing according their behaviors

1. Unconventional Testing
2. Conventional Testing

Unconventional Testing

Unconventional testing is a process of verification which is doing by SQA (Software Quality Assurance) team. It is a prevention technique which is performing from begging to ending of the project development. In this process SQA team verifies project development activities and insuring that developing project is fulfilling the requirement of the client or not.

Conventional Testing

Conventional Testing is a process of finding the bugs and validating the project. Testing team involves in this testing process and validating that developed project is according to client requirement or not. This process is a

correction technique where testing team find bugs and reporting to the development team for correction on developed project built.

7.2 TEST CASE DESIGN

7.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit testing involves the design of test cases that validate that the internal program logic is functioning properly, and that program input produces valid outputs. All decision branches and internal code flow should be validated. It is the testing of individual software units of the application .it is done after the completion of an individual unit before integration. This is a structural testing, that relies on knowledge of its construction and is invasive. Unit tests perform basic tests at component level and test a specific business process, application, and/or system configuration. Unit tests ensure that each unique path of a business process performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results.

7.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional tests provide systematic demonstrations that functions tested are available as specified by the business and technical requirements, system documentation, and user manuals. Functional testing is centered on the following items:

- Valid Input : identified classes of valid input must be accepted.
- Invalid Input : identified classes of invalid input must be rejected.
- Functions : identified functions must be exercised.
- Output : identified classes of application outputs must be exercised.
- Systems/Procedures : interfacing systems or procedures must be invoked.

7.2.3 System Testing

System testing ensures that the entire integrated software system meets requirements. It tests a configuration to ensure known and predictable results.

An example of system testing is the configuration oriented system integration test. System testing is based on process descriptions and flows, emphasizing pre-driven process links and integration points.

7.2.4 Acceptance Testing

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

Acceptance testing for Data Synchronization:

- The Acknowledgements will be received by the Sender Node after the Packets are received by the Destination Node.
- The Route add operation is done only when there is a Route request in need.
- The Status of Nodes information is done automatically in the Cache Updation process.

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system will detect the disease affected by the leaf in the sugarcane plant i.e to reduce the disease rate in crop .By taking image of plant that is effected we will apply the dwt algorithm and will start the process by capturing the image by using digital camera. After capturing the image have to be enhanced by clearing the noise and from here the detection part starts by applying image segmentation after that classifying the diseases in image. In this project the detection of plant disease are done.

Simple fourier transform is used to form matrix and eliminate the green pixels in the image and highlight the affected area so that the detection will be easy.

Initially, disease affected dataset image is considered as the input with RGB color value. Then image is enhanced using histogram equalization by distributing the intensity of the image using cumulative distribution function. Then image intensity is restored to get enhanced image. This enhanced image is segmented using k-means clustering in the form of three segments as disease affected ROI, Unaffected ROI and rest background ROI. From these segments, disease affected image portion is considered to check the type of disease and to find out the percentage of disease affected portion. For this, image features are extracted by maintaining the Grey Level Occurrence Matrices (GLCMs). In this matrix, we are maintaining the disease symptoms by calculating the feature values of Skewness, Standard_Deviation, Homogeneity, Contrast, Smoothness, Correlation, Kurtosis, Energy, Entropy, Mean, Variance, RMS, and IDM. Based on these values feature are matches with expert dataset values.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

9.1 CONCLUSION

An application of texture analysis in detecting and classifying the plant leaf diseases has been explained in this paper. Thus the proposed algorithm was tested on ten disease of sugarcane plant namely Eyespot Disease, Leaf Scald, Mosaic, Orange Rust, Pineapple Disease , Pokkah Boeng Disease, Ratoon Stunting. Red –Rot Disease. The diseases specific to those plants were taken for our approach. The experimental results indicate the proposed approach can recognize and classify the leaf diseases with a little computational effort. Based on the analysis, gray scale images are easy to process and implement. They have better clarity and suited for analysis than RGB images. Histogram equalization is used to enhance the contrast of the images and provides clear image to human eyes. So, these types of images will be used to analyse and diagnosis the plant leaves diseases and determines the diseases level of the plant leaves. Mobile phone has become available at the grass-root level providing different social and economic benefit. The aim of this proposal was to develop a user friendly automated system for the farmers that will help them in determining detection diseases of leaves without bringing an expert to the field.

9.2 Future Enhancement

Support vector machine is used to find out the type of disease by matching with the feature classes. Also the percentage of disease affected portion is evaluated. Finally optimization is performed to find out the accuracy of results. For this optimization process, we have used ant colony optimization with the local and global solution. To find out the global solution, we have considered 500 iterations values.

APPENDICES

A. SAMPLE CODE

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function varargout = GrapeLeaf(varargin)
% GRAPELEAF MATLAB code for GrapeLeaf.fig
%   GRAPELEAF, by itself, creates a new GRAPELEAF or raises the existing
%   singleton*.
%
%   H = GRAPELEAF returns the handle to a new GRAPELEAF or the handle to
%   the existing singleton*.
%
%   GRAPELEAF('CALLBACK',hObject,eventData,handles,...) calls the local
%   function named CALLBACK in GRAPELEAF.M with the given input
arguments.
%
%   GRAPELEAF('Property','Value',...) creates a new GRAPELEAF or raises the
%   existing singleton*. Starting from the left, property value pairs are
%   applied to the GUI before GrapeLeaf_OpeningFcn gets called. An
%   unrecognized property name or invalid value makes property application
%   stop. All inputs are passed to GrapeLeaf_OpeningFcn via varargin.
%
%   *See GUI Options on GUIDE's Tools menu. Choose "GUI allows only one
%   instance to run (singleton)".
%
% See also: GUIDE, GUIDATA, GUIHANDLES

% Edit the above text to modify the response to help GrapeLeaf

% Last Modified by GUIDE v2.5 28-Apr-2018 16:39:21

% Begin initialization code - DO NOT EDIT
gui_Singleton = 1;
gui_State = struct('gui_Name',    mfilename, ...
                  'gui_Singleton', gui_Singleton, ...
                  'gui_OpeningFcn', @GrapeLeaf_OpeningFcn, ...
                  'gui_OutputFcn', @GrapeLeaf_OutputFcn, ...
                  'gui_LayoutFcn', [] , ...
                  'gui_Callback', []);
if nargin && ischar(varargin{1})
    gui_State.gui_Callback = str2func(varargin{1});
end

if nargout
    [varargout{1:nargout}] = gui_mainfcn(gui_State, varargin{:});
else
    gui_mainfcn(gui_State, varargin{:});
end
% End initialization code - DO NOT EDIT
```

```

% --- Executes just before GrapeLeaf is made visible.
function GrapeLeaf_OpeningFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles, varargin)
% This function has no output args, see OutputFcn.
% hObject    handle to figure
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
% varargin   command line arguments to GrapeLeaf (see VARARGIN)

% Choose default command line output for GrapeLeaf
handles.output = hObject;

% Update handles structure
guidata(hObject, handles);

% UIWAIT makes GrapeLeaf wait for user response (see UIRESUME)
% uiwait(handles.figure1);

% --- Outputs from this function are returned to the command line.
function varargout = GrapeLeaf_OutputFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% varargout  cell array for returning output args (see VARARGOUT);
% hObject    handle to figure
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Get default command line output from handles structure
varargout{1} = handles.output;

function edit1_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to edit1 (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)

% Hints: get(hObject,'String') returns contents of edit1 as text
%        str2double(get(hObject,'String')) returns contents of edit1 as a double

% --- Executes during object creation, after setting all properties.
function edit1_CreateFcn(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to edit1 (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles    empty - handles not created until after all CreateFcns called

% Hint: edit controls usually have a white background on Windows.
%       See ISPC and COMPUTER.
if ispc && isequal(get(hObject,'BackgroundColor'),
get(0,'defaultUicontrolBackgroundColor'))

```

```
set(hObject,'BackgroundColor','white');
end
```

```
% --- Executes on button press in pushbutton2.
function pushbutton2_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject handle to pushbutton2 (see GCBO)
% eventdata reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
[file]=uigetfile('*.jpg','Select the image');
a=imread(file);
b=imresize(a,[256 256]);
c=rgb2gray(b);
axes(handles.axes1)
imhist(c)
title('Histogram')
d=histeq(c);
axes(handles.axes2)
imshow(d)
title('Histogram Equalization')
H = fspecial('gaussian',[3 3],.5);
e = imfilter(d,H);
axes(handles.axes3)
imshow(e);
title('Filtering - Gaussian')
thresholdValue = 150;
j=im2bw(e,.7);
axes(handles.axes4)
imshow(j)
title('Segmentation')
h=edge(j,'canny');
axes(handles.axes6)
imshow(h)
title('Edge Detection')
q1=imread('1sugarcane ring rot.jpg');
q2=imread('2brown stripe .jpg');
q3=imread('3.sugarcane leafscald.jpg');
q4=imread('4 downy mildew.jpg');
q5=imread('5 eye spot .jpg ');
q6=imread('6.smut disease.jpg');
q7=imread('7pineapple disease .jpg');
q8=imread('8.sugarcane orange rust.jpg');
q9=imread('9 pokkahboeng disease .jpg ');
q10=imread('10ratoon stunning .jpg ');
q11=imread('11sugarcane brown leafsopt.jpg');
q12=imread('12 sugarcane red rot.jpg');
q13=imread('13 sugarcane yellow leaf disease .jpg');
r1=rgb2gray(q1);
r2=rgb2gray(q2);
r3=rgb2gray(q3);
```

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r4=rgb2gray(q4);
r5=rgb2gray(q5);
r6=rgb2gray(q6);
r7=rgb2gray(q7);
r8=rgb2gray(q8);
r9=rgb2gray(q9);
r10=rgb2gray(q10);
r11=rgb2gray(q11);
r12=rgb2gray(q12);
r13=rgb2gray(q13);
t1=imresize(r1,[256 256]);
t2=imresize(r2,[256 256]);
t3=imresize(r3,[256 256]);
t4=imresize(r4,[256 256]);
t5=imresize(r5,[256 256]);
t6=imresize(r6,[256 256]);
t7=imresize(r7,[256 256]);
t8=imresize(r8,[256 256]);
t9=imresize(r9,[256 256]);
t10=imresize(r10,[256 256]);
t11=imresize(r11,[256 256]);
t12=imresize(r12,[256 256]);
t13=imresize(r13,[256 256]);
y1=corr2(h,t1);
y2=corr2(h,t2);
y3=corr2(h,t3);
y4=corr2(h,t4);
y5=corr2(h,t5);
y6=corr2(h,t6);
y7=corr2(h,t7);
y8=corr2(h,t8);
y9=corr2(h,t9);
y10=corr2(h,t10);
y11=corr2(h,t11);
y12=corr2(h,t12);
y13=corr2(h,t13);
yt=[y1 y2 y3 y4 y5 y6 y7 y8 y9 y10 y11 y12 y13];
ytm=max(yt);
if ytm==y1
    axes(handles.axes5)
    imshow(q1);
    title('Equivalent Image');
    msgbox('sugarcane ring rot');
else if ytm==y2
    axes(handles.axes5)
    imshow(q2);
    title('Equivalent Image');
    msgbox('brown stripe');
else if ytm==y3
    axes(handles.axes5)

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imshow(q3);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('sugarcane leafscald');
else if ytm==y4
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q4);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('downy mildew');
else if ytm==y5
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q5);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('eye spot');
else if ytm==y6
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q6);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('smut disease');
else if ytm==y7
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q7);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('pineapple disease');
else if ytm==y8
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q8);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('sugarcane orange rust');
else if ytm==y9
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q9);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('pokkahboeng disease');
else if ytm==y10
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q10);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('ratoon stunning');
else if ytm==y11
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q11);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('sugarcane brown leafsopt');
else if ytm==y12
axes(handles.axes5)
imshow(q12);
title('Equivalent Image');
  msgbox('sugarcane red rot');
else if ytm==y13
axes(handles.axes5)

```

```

imshow(q13);
title('Equivalent Image');
msgbox('sugarcane yellow leaf disease');
    end
    end
end
end
% --- Executes on button press in pushbutton3.
function pushbutton3_Callback(hObject, eventdata, handles)
% hObject    handle to pushbutton3 (see GCBO)
% eventdata  reserved - to be defined in a future version of MATLAB
% handles    structure with handles and user data (see GUIDATA)
[file]=uigetfile('*.jpg','Select the image');
a=imread(file);
b=imresize(a,[256 256]);
c=rgb2gray(b);
figure,imshow(c)
title('Gray Image')
d=histeq(c);
H = fspecial('gaussian',[3 3],.5);
e = imfilter(d,H);
thresholdValue = 150;
j=im2bw(e,.7);
figure,imshow(j)
title('Segmented Image')

```

B.SCREENSHOTS

Image loading:

Threshold value

Invert blue

Edge detector:

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